

854 **Supplementals:**

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856 **Bacterial pathogens dynamic during multi-species infections**

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860 FigS1: Bacterial multiplication in TBS medium

861 FigS2: Result at strain level of the 16 synthetic communities after growth on TSB.

862 FigS3: Result at strain level of the 16 synthetic communities 5 days post inoculation on potato
863 tubers.

864 File S1: supplemental modeling

865 Table S1: strains description

866 Table S2: Intra-species strain discrimination with the 341 nt gapA barcode

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871 **Figure S1:** Bacterial multiplication in TBS medium.

872 For each tested communities (3 replicates), the bacterial load at time zero (inoculum) and at the end of
873 the experiment were used to calculate the number of bacterial generation achieved ($\log_{10}(\text{cfu end}$
874 $\text{experiment}/\text{cfu T0})/\log_{10}(2)$). The *P. aquaticum* and *P. versatile* communities are compared. The result
875 of the statistical analysis is represented by the letters (a, b) at the top of the boxplots. The bacterial
876 mixtures sharing the same letter(s) are not statistically different from each other ($P > 0.05$ Kruskal Wallis
877 followed by Dunn test with the Bonferroni correction).

879

880 **Figure S2:** Result at strain level of the 16 synthetic communities after growth on TSB.

881 The proportion of each strain (or mix of strains when strains could not be differentiated by the *gapA*
 882 barcode) is indicated in the legend of each graph. The 2 columns represent the proportion of strains
 883 observed in the inoculum (T0) and after 48h of growth in TSB medium (48) for each tested synthetic
 884 community. Error bar on the second column (48) represent the standard error observed for the 3
 885 replicates. The 16 different tested communities are as follow: AQUA-ATRO: mix of 3 *P. aquaticum*

886 strains and 3 *P. atrosepticum* strains; AQUA-BRASI: mix of 3 *P. aquaticum* strains and 3 *P. brasiliense*
887 strains; AQUA-CARO: mix of 3 *P. aquaticum* strains and 3 *P. carotovorum* strains; AQUA-DIAN: mix
888 of 3 *P. aquaticum* strains and 3 *D. dianthicola* strains; AQUA-PARM: mix of 3 *P. aquaticum* strains
889 and 3 *P. parmentieri* strains; AQUA-POL: mix of 3 *P. aquaticum* strains, 1 *P. polaris* and 2 *P. parvum*
890 strains; AQUA-SOL: mix of 3 *P. aquaticum* strains and 3 *D. solani* strains, AQUA-VERS: mix of 3 *P.*
891 *aquaticum* strains and 3 *P. versatile* strains; VERS-AQUA: mix of 3 *P. versatile* strains and 3 *P.*
892 *aquaticum* strains; VERS-ATRO: mix of 3 *P. versatile* strains and 3 *P. atrosepticum* strains; VERS-
893 BRASI: mix of 3 *P. versatile* strains and 3 *P. brasiliense* strains; VERS-DIAN: mix of 3 *P. versatile*
894 strains and 3 *D. dianthicola* strains; VERS-CARO: mix of 3 *P. versatile* strains and 3 *P. carotovorum*
895 strains; VERS-PARM: mix of 3 *P. versatile* strains and 3 *P. parmentieri* strains; VERS-POL: mix of 3
896 *P. versatile* strains, 1 *P. polaris* and 2 *P. parvum* strains; VERS-SOL: mix of 3 *P. versatile* strains and
897 3 *D. solani* strains. The strains used in each bacterial mixture are listed in Table S1.
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900

901 **Figure S3:** Result at strain level of the 16 synthetic communities 5 days post inoculation on potato
 902 tubers.

903 The proportion of each strain (or mix of strains when strains could not be differentiated by the *gapA*
 904 barcode) is indicated in the legend of each graph. The 2 columns represent the proportion of strains
 905 observed in the inoculum (T0) and after 5 days after inoculation within potato tubers (5 dpi) for each
 906 tested synthetic community. Error bar on the second column (5 dpi) represent the standard error observed

907 for the 3 to 6 inoculated potato tubers. The 16 different tested communities are as follow: AQUA-ATRO:
908 mix of 3 *P. aquaticum* strains and 3 *P. atrosepticum* strains; AQUA-BRASI: mix of 3 *P. aquaticum*
909 strains and 3 *P. brasiliense* strains; AQUA-CARO: mix of 3 *P. aquaticum* strains and 3 *P. carotovorum*
910 strains; AQUA-DIAN: mix of 3 *P. aquaticum* strains and 3 *D. dianthicola* strains; AQUA-PARM: mix
911 of 3 *P. aquaticum* strains and 3 *P. parmentieri* strains; AQUA-POL: mix of 3 *P. aquaticum* strains, 1 *P.*
912 *polaris* and 2 *P. parvum* strains; AQUA-SOL: mix of 3 *P. aquaticum* strains and 3 *D. solani* strains,
913 AQUA-VERS: mix of 3 *P. aquaticum* strains and 3 *P. versatile* strains; VERS-AQUA: mix of 3 *P.*
914 *versatile* strains and 3 *P. aquaticum* strains; VERS-ATRO: mix of 3 *P. versatile* strains and 3 *P.*
915 *atrosepticum* strains; VERS-BRASI: mix of 3 *P. versatile* strains and 3 *P. brasiliense* strains; VERS-
916 DIAN: mix of 3 *P. versatile* strains and 3 *D. dianthicola* strains; VERS-CARO: mix of 3 *P. versatile*
917 strains and 3 *P. carotovorum* strains; VERS-PARM: mix of 3 *P. versatile* strains and 3 *P. parmentieri*
918 strains; VERS-POL: mix of 3 *P. versatile* strains, 1 *P. polaris* and 2 *P. parvum* strains; VERS-SOL: mix
919 of 3 *P. versatile* strains and 3 *D. solani* strains. The strains used in each bacterial mixture are listed in
920 Table S1.
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922 **File S1:** supplemental modeling.

Supplementary materials for the model analyzing the coexistence between a producer of degraded substrate and a cheater

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December 5, 2023

1 Description of the model

The equations of the model are:

$$\frac{dD_X}{dt} = k(D_R - D_X) - (g_A - \epsilon)D_X X + \frac{cX}{z + X}$$

$$\frac{dD_A}{dt} = k(D_R - D_A) - g_A D_A A$$

$$\frac{dD_R}{dt} = -k(2D_R - D_X - D_A) - \lambda D_R$$

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = (g_A - \epsilon)D_X X - mX$$

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = g_A D_A A - mA$$

with X the density of the species that produces enzymes able to degrade the substrate, A the density of the cheater species that only consumes the degraded substrate without being able to produce it, D_X is the concentration of degraded substrate in the vicinity of species X (i.e. local pool of degraded substrate of X), D_A is the corresponding local substrate pool for A , and D_R is the concentration of degraded substrate in the regional environmental (hereafter regional pool of degraded substrate). The parameters of the model are described in table 1.

Table 1: Definition of the parameters of the model and their corresponding values as used in the numerical simulations (results in the figures of main text and supplementary materials)

Parameter	Definition	Value
k	Transport rate of degraded substrate between local and regional pools	5, 50
c	Maximum rate of enzymatic substrate degradation	[0,5]
z	Half-saturation constant of enzymatic substrate degradation	1
g_A	Consumption rate of degraded substrate without cost	2
ϵ	Cost of enzyme production on consumption rate of degraded substrate	[0,1.9]
m	Mortality rate of x and A	0.1
λ	Loss of degraded substrate from regional pool	1

2 Mathematical analysis of the model

The table 2 below describes the equilibria of the model. Please note that by definition we always have $\epsilon < g_A$ (i.e. the growth rate of X in relation to the consumption of degraded substrate is always positive).

The results described in Table 1 indicate that, as expected, the cheater species A cannot persist without the producer species X . In addition, the persistence of species A requires that the cost

Table 2: The different equilibria of the model. While the equilibria could be calculated mathematically, stability was only assessed with numerical simulations and thus the details indicated in this case might not correspond to all possible cases. We have $B = k(D_R - D_X) - zm + c$ and $\Delta = B^2 - 4(g_A - \epsilon)zk(D_X - D_R) < B^2$.

Equilibrium	D_X	D_A	D_R	A	X	Feasibility conditions	Stability
No A, no X	0	0	0	0	0		yes
No A, low X	$\frac{m}{g_A - \epsilon}$	D_R	$\frac{k}{k + \lambda} D_X$	0	$\frac{B - \sqrt{\Delta}}{(g_A - \epsilon) D_X}$	$c > D_X \frac{\lambda}{\lambda + k} + zm$ $\Delta > 0$	no
No A, high X	$\frac{m}{g_A - \epsilon}$	D_R	$\frac{k}{k + \lambda} D_X$	0	$\frac{B + \sqrt{\Delta}}{(g_A - \epsilon) D_X}$	$c > D_X \frac{\lambda}{\lambda + k} + zm$ $\Delta > 0$	yes if $\epsilon < \frac{\lambda g_A}{k + \lambda}$
A, no X	D_R	$\frac{m}{g_A}$	$\frac{k}{k + \lambda} D_A$	$\frac{k(D_R - D_A)}{g_A D_A}$	0	never feasible, $A < 0$	NA
A, low X	$\frac{m}{g_A - \epsilon}$	$\frac{m}{g_A}$	$\frac{k}{k + \lambda} D_A$	$\frac{k(D_R - D_A)}{g_A D_A}$	$\frac{B - \sqrt{\Delta}}{(g_A - \epsilon) D_X}$	$\epsilon > \frac{\lambda g_A}{k + \lambda}$ (for $A > 0$) $c > zm + D_X \frac{k(k\epsilon + \lambda g_A)}{(\lambda + 2k)g_A}$ $\Delta > 0$ (for $X > 0$)	no
A, high X	$\frac{m}{g_A - \epsilon}$	$\frac{m}{g_A}$	$\frac{k}{k + \lambda} D_A$	$\frac{k(D_R - D_A)}{g_A D_A}$	$\frac{B + \sqrt{\Delta}}{(g_A - \epsilon) D_X}$	$\epsilon > \frac{\lambda g_A}{k + \lambda}$ (for $A > 0$) $c > zm + D_X \frac{k(k\epsilon + \lambda g_A)}{(\lambda + 2k)g_A}$ $\Delta > 0$ (for $X > 0$)	yes

sustained by X for enzyme production for the substrate degradation (ϵ) is higher than a given proportion of the maximum consumption rate of degraded substrate (g_A). The lower the transport rate k of degraded substrate between regional and local pools and the higher the loss of degraded substrate λ , the higher the cost ϵ required for the persistence of A. Meanwhile, the persistence of X with A requires that the maximum rate of substrate degradation by X (c) is higher than a threshold defined by most model parameters. In particular, this threshold increases with the cost sustained by X for enzyme production for the substrate degradation (ϵ) and with the transport rate k of degraded substrate between regional and local pools.

3 Numerical simulations of the model

To illustrate the results of the model, we calculated the equilibrium values for the range of parameters detailed in Table 1. The stability of each equilibrium was assessed by computing the eigenvalues of the Jacobian matrix at equilibrium. We also performed numerical integration of the model using the function `lsoda` from the R package `deSolve` to investigate the temporal dynamics of the two species and of the resource pools for a few study cases.

Figure 1: Densities at equilibrium of the producer species X (left) and of the cheater species A (right) as a function of the maximum rate of substrate degradation by X (c) and the cost of enzyme production on the growth rate of X (ϵ) for $k = 50$ (high flow of substrate between regional and local pools).

Figure 2: Temporal dynamics of the species densities and the concentration of degraded substrate in the local and regional pools in two case studies with $k = 50$ and $\epsilon = 1$. Left panels: Coexistence of X and A at equilibrium ($c = 3$). Right panels: Extinction of both X and A ($c = 1$).

926 **Table S1:** Strains description.

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Species	Strain	Isolated from	year	Genome accession
<i>P. aquaticum</i>	A101-S19-F16	River water	2016	GCA_003382625.2
<i>P. aquaticum</i>	A127-S21-F16	River water	2016	GCA_003382655.2
<i>P. aquaticum</i>	A212-S19-A16 ^T	River water	2016	GCA_003382565.3
<i>P. versatile</i>	A73-S18-O15	River water	2015	GCA_020865565.1
<i>P. versatile</i>	CFBP5663	<i>Iris</i>	1983	GCA_004296765.1
<i>P. versatile</i>	CFBP6051 ^T	<i>solanum tuberosum</i>	NA	GCA_004296685.1
<i>D. dianthicola</i>	MIE34	Not available		GCA_009874285.1
<i>D. dianthicola</i>	CFBP2015	<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	1975	GCA_009873535.1
<i>D. dianthicola</i>	CFBP1888	<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	1978	GCA_009873515.1
<i>D. solani</i>	CC3239	Not available		Not available
<i>D. solani</i>	PPO9019	Not available		GCA_002846995.1
<i>D. solani</i>	CFBP8199 ^T	<i>solanum tuberosum</i>	2007	Not available
<i>P. parmentieri</i>	CFBP8475 ^T	<i>solanum tuberosum</i>	2008	GCA_001742145.1
<i>P. parmentieri</i>	CFBP5382	<i>solanum tuberosum</i>	1997	Not available
<i>P. parmentieri</i>	CFBP1338	<i>solanum tuberosum</i>	NA	Not available
<i>P. atrosepticum</i>	CFBP1453	<i>Lycopersicon esculentum</i>	1973	Not available
<i>P. atrosepticum</i>	CFBP1527	<i>solanum tuberosum</i>	1973	Not available
<i>P. atrosepticum</i>	CFBP7375	<i>solanum tuberosum</i>	2004	Not available
<i>P. brasiliense</i>	CFBP5381	<i>solanum tuberosum</i>	1997	GCA_013449475.1
<i>P. brasiliense</i>	CFBP3230	<i>Gossypium sp.</i>	1964	GCA_013449485.1
<i>P. brasiliense</i>	CFBP6617 ^T	<i>solanum tuberosum</i>	1999	GCA_009873295.1
<i>P. carotovorum</i>	CFBP1402	<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	1972	GCA_013449385.1
<i>P. carotovorum</i>	CFBP6074	<i>solanum tuberosum</i>	NA	GCA_013449495.1
<i>P. carotovorum</i>	CFBP2046 ^T	<i>solanum tuberosum</i>	1952	GCA_000749855.1 *
<i>P. polaris</i>	CFBP1403	<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	1969	Not available
<i>P. parvum</i>	CFBP8630 ^T	<i>solanum tuberosum</i>	NA	GCA_900195285.2
<i>P. parvum</i>	CFBP6058	<i>solanum tuberosum</i>	NA	GCA_000749915.1

928 * Deposited under the name NCPPB312

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930 **Table S2:** Intra-species strain discrimination with the 341 nt gapA barcode.

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species	strain	Nb of strain specific nucleotide (primer excluded)	Intra-species discrimination
<i>P. aquaticum</i>	A101	1	Discriminate the 3 strains
<i>P. aquaticum</i>	A127	1	
<i>P. aquaticum</i>	A212-ST	0	
<i>P. versatile</i>	A73E	0	Discriminate CFBP5663
<i>P. versatile</i>	CFBP5663	2	
<i>P. versatile</i>	CFBP6051 ^T	0	
<i>D. dianthicola</i>	MIE34	0	No discrimination
<i>D. dianthicola</i>	CFBP2015	0	
<i>D. dianthicola</i>	CFBP1888	0	
<i>D. solani</i>	CC3239	0	No discrimination
<i>D. solani</i>	PPO9019	0	
<i>D. solani</i>	CFBP8199 ^T	0	
<i>P. parmentieri</i>	CFBP8475 ^T	1	Discriminate CFBP8475
<i>P. parmentieri</i>	CFBP5382	0	
<i>P. parmentieri</i>	CFBP1338	0	
<i>P. atrosepticum</i>	CFBP1453	0	Discriminate CFBP7375
<i>P. atrosepticum</i>	CFBP1527	0	
<i>P. atrosepticum</i>	CFBP7375	22	
<i>P. brasiliense</i>	CFBP5381	0	Discriminate the 3 strains
<i>P. brasiliense</i>	CFBP3230	3	
<i>P. brasiliense</i>	CFBP6617 ^T	2	
<i>P. carotovorum</i>	CFBP1402	0	Discriminate CFBP2046
<i>P. carotovorum</i>	CFBP6074	0	
<i>P. carotovorum</i>	CFBP2046 ^T	2	
<i>P. polaris</i>	CFBP1403	0	No discrimination
<i>P. parvum</i>	CFBP8630 ^T	0	
<i>P. parvum</i>	CFBP6058	0	

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